

Data User's Guide: Seed origin and warming constrain lodgepole pine recruitment, slowing the pace of population range shifts

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Data Summary

This data package contains data that were used to support conclusions drawn in “Seed origin and warming constrain lodgepole pine recruitment, slowing the pace of population range shifts”, by Conlisk *et al.* 2018. Experimental data collected at field sites within the Alpine Treeline Warming Experiment (ATWE) on Niwot Ridge, Colorado, USA were used to formulate models packaged within “Model_archive” in the zipped folder “Conlisk_etal_GCB2018_model_archive20201202.zip”.

“Model_archive” contains four comma-separated values (.csv) files used to create Figures 4 and 6 in the published journal, and five folders that contain population model files. These files can be opened with either a text-editor software, or Microsoft Excel. Models are stored as text files (.txt), and .pch, .sch, and .fch files can also be opened as text files using any simple text-editor software. However, please note that all the aforementioned files are specific to the RAMAS’ population modeling software suite, and you will need the software in order to be able to run the models. Analyses for this publication utilized Metapop.

Experimental seedling and microclimate data are available in files “PICOseedlings20160408rev20210127” and “Climate_Table_d0_v20160607EEC_rev20210803”, respectively. Both files are available in .csv and .xlsx formats, and zipped in their respective folders. Data files with the same name are identical; file formats are provided for accessibility. “PICOseedlings...” contain lodgepole pine seedling data that were used for analysis and model parameterization, while “Climate_Table...” files contain delta values presented in Table 1 of the publication. The respective files can be opened using any simple text-editor software, and Microsoft Excel.

“StatsPICO06072016rev12212020.R” is an R script file containing code used for statistical analyses reported in the final manuscript; R version 3.3.3 was used. The file can be opened by R, RStudio, and simple text-editor software. Some calculations were not used in the publication, and are indicated in the file.

As above, “gcb13840-sup-0001-supinfo” is archived here in two forms: Microsoft Word (.docx) and PDF. The file contents are identical, and different file formats are provided for greater flexibility in file access. The .docx file can be opened by Microsoft Word, and the PDF can be opened by Adobe Acrobat Reader, or any application compatible with PDF files.

Geospatial data delineating the three study sites are also included in this archive: .kml files can be opened by Google Earth or Google Maps, and shapefiles (.shp) can be opened by geospatial information systems applications compatible with shapefiles, such as ESRI’s ArcGIS suite, and QGIS.

All files in this archive are briefly listed and described below. For more details, visit the Data Characteristics and Data Dictionary sections below.

PICO_seedling_data.zip contains the following:

- Two files, both named “PICOseedlings20160408rev20210127”; one is in .csv form and the other is in Microsoft Excel (.xlsx) form. These data were used for analysis of experimental results presented in Tables 2 and 3 and Figures 2 and 3, and for model parameterization purposes.
- Data inputting was completed on April 8 of 2016, and additional reviews were completed December 19 of 2020.
- Data in both files are identical. The Microsoft Excel format of the file contains an extra sheet within the workbook indicating column headers and their descriptions. A similar description table can be found in the “Data Dictionary” section of this guide.

StatsPICO06072016rev12212020.R

- This file contains the R script of the statistical calculations made for the publication.
- The script is separated into different sections, labeled to show what was calculated, and where the results are published (either in the main publication, or in the supplementary materials “gcb13840-sup-0001-supinfo.docx/.pdf” files, also in this archive).

Fig4ace_PICO_hi_20degrees.csv

- This file contains the model output results that went into Figure 4, panels a, c, and e.
- These figure panels are meant to simulate seed rain from a high-elevation seed provenance (~3,300m).
- The models were parameterized using the recruitment rates observed across forest, treeline, and alpine sites (as in Figure 2 of the main text).
- There are 12 sets of model results: four future scenarios analogous to the four experimental treatments (control, heating, watering, and heating+watering) at each of the three sites (forest, treeline, and alpine).

Fig4bdf_PICO_lo_20degrees.csv

- This file contains the model output results that went into Figure 4 panels b, d, and f.
- The columns in this file are analogous to those in the file above, but instead simulate a low-elevation seed provenance (~2,970m).

Fig6ace_PICO_hi_20degrees_FIRE.csv

- This file contains the model output results that went into Figure 6 panels a, c, and e.
- The columns in this file are analogous to those in the hi provenance file above, but instead simulate a high-elevation seed provenance, *with a fire that occurs in year 50 of the 500-year time horizon.*

Fig6bdf_PICO_lo_20degrees_FIRE.csv

- This file contains the model output results that went into Figure 6 panels b, d, and f.
- The columns in this file are analogous to those in the low provenance file above, but instead simulate a low-elevation seed provenance, *with a fire that occurs in year 50 of the 500-year time horizon.*

Folder Fire_HighProv contains the following:

- This folder contains all model files for the high provenance, fire models.
- Four model files, saved as text files, for the four model scenarios reflecting the four experimental treatments: (i) control (eg “Fig6ace_PICO_FIRE_control_hi_20degrees.txt”), (ii) watering, (iii) heating, and (iv) heating and watering.
To make the text file work as a population model file, the extension needs to be switched from “.txt” to “.mp”, where the latter is the metapopulation modeling file extension for the RAMAS software. *Please see the ‘Contents of a text file used by RAMAS’ below for intuition about the lines of text in this file.*
- Files “Conifer_2014.dpr” and “Conifer_low_mort_2014.dll” are used to implement density-dependent mortality in the treeline patch. Only the “.dll” is needed for the model, but the “.dpr” file is included for compiling one’s own “.dll” file.
- Six files with extensions “.sch” (e.g. “PICO_ALP_Hi_Heating.sch”); these describe changes in survival through time because of the influence of heating over the 21st Century. Two scenarios, meant to reflect experimental treatments, involved heating (heating, and heating with extra watering), which were crossed by the three sites (forest - LSA, treeline - USA, and alpine - ALP).
- One file with extension “.fch” (e.g. “PICO_FIRE_seeds_3yrs.fch”), which describes changes in fecundity following a fire. Short-term seed availability is increased because lodgepole serotinous cones release their seeds following a fire.
- One file with extension “.pch” (e.g. “PICO_post_fire.pch”), which describes changes in recruitment following a fire. Recruitment is increased because lodgepole recruitment is assumed to be stimulated by an open canopy.
- The results of these models are in the csv file “Fig6ace_PICO_hi_20degrees_FIRE.csv”, and are shown in Figure 6a, c, and e of the main text.

Folder Fire_LoProv contains the following:

- This folder contains all model files for the low provenance, fire models.
- Files “Conifer_2014.dpr” and “Conifer_low_mort_2014.dll” are used to implement density-dependent mortality in the treeline patch. Only the “.dll” is needed for the model, but the “.dpr” file is included for compiling one’s own “.dll” file.
- Four model files, saved as text files, for the four model scenarios reflecting the four experimental treatments: (i) control (eg “Fig6bdf_PICO_FIRE_control_lo_20degrees.txt”), (ii) watering, (iii) heating, and (iv) heating and watering.
To make the text file work as a population model file, the extension needs to be switched from “.txt” to “.mp”, where the latter is the metapopulation modeling file extension for the RAMAS software. *Please see the ‘Contents of a text file used by RAMAS’ below for intuition about the lines of text in this file.*
- Six files with extensions “.sch” (e.g. “PICO_ALP_Lo_Heating.sch”); these describe changes in survival through time because of the influence of heating over the 21st Century. Two scenarios, meant to reflect experimental treatments, involved heating (heating, and heating with extra watering), which were crossed by the three sites (forest - LSA, treeline - USA, and alpine - ALP).
- A file with extension “.fch” (e.g. “PICO_FIRE_seeds_3yrs.fch”), which describes changes in fecundity following a fire. Short-term seed availability is increased because lodgepole serotinous cones release their seeds following a fire.

- A file with extension “.pch” (e.g. “PICO_post_fire.pch”), which describes changes in recruitment following a fire. Recruitment is increased because lodgepole recruitment is assumed to be stimulated by an open canopy.
- The results of these models are in spreadsheet “**Fig6bdf_PICO_lo_20degrees_FIRE.csv**” and Figure 6b, d, and f of the main text.

Folder NoFire_HiProv contains the following:

- This folder contains all model files for the low provenance, no fire models. It differs from the two FIRE folders above because there are no files to implement post-fire impacts.
- File “Conifer_low_mort_2014.dll” is used to implement density-dependent mortality in the treeline patch.
- Four model files, saved as text files, for the four model scenarios reflecting the four experimental treatments: (i) control (eg “Fig4ace_PICO_control_hi_20degrees.txt”), (ii) watering, (iii) heating, and (iv) heating and watering. To make the text file work as a population model file, the extension needs to be switched from “.txt” to “.mp”, where the latter is the metapopulation modeling file extension for the RAMAS software.
- Six files with extensions “.sch” (e.g. “PICO_ALP_Hi_Heating.sch”). These describe changes in survival through time because of the influence of heating. Two scenarios - meant to reflect experimental treatment - involved heating (heating, and heating with extra watering), which were crossed by the three sites (forest - LSA, treeline - USA, and alpine - ALP).
- The results of these models are in spreadsheet “**Fig4ace_PICO_hi_20degrees.csv**” and Figure 4a, c, and e of the main text.

Folder NoFire_LoProv contains the following:

- This folder contains all model files for the low provenance, no fire models. It differs from the two FIRE folders above because there are no files to implement post-fire impacts.
- File “Conifer_low_mort_2014.dll” is used to implement density-dependent mortality in the treeline patch.
- Four model files, saved as text files, for the four model scenarios reflecting the four experimental treatments: (i) control (eg “Fig4bdf_PICO_control_lo_20degrees.txt”), (ii) watering, (iii) heating, and (iv) heating and watering. To make the text file work as a population model file, the extension needs to be switched from “.txt” to “.mp”, where the latter is the metapopulation modeling file extension for the RAMAS software.
- Six files with extensions “.sch” (e.g. “PICO_ALP_Lo_Heating.sch”), these describe changes in survival through time because of the influence of heating. Two scenarios, meant to reflect experimental treatments, involved heating (heating, and heating with extra watering), which were crossed by the three sites (forest - LSA, treeline - USA, and alpine - ALP).
- The results of these models are in spreadsheet “**Fig4bdf_PICO_lo_20degrees.csv**” and Figure 4b, d, and f of the main text.

Folder NoFire_InclineAngle contains the following:

- This folder contains all model files for the low and high provenance, no fire, incline angle models. There are no files to implement post-fire impacts, because there are no fires in these scenarios.
- File “Conifer_low_mort_2014.dll” is used to implement density-dependent mortality in the treeline patch.
- Only the heating and watering scenario is run.
- Model files in this folder are saved as text files (.txt). There are two provenance model scenarios: high and low; each scenario was run in seven 5-degree incline angle increments, which affects the dispersal distances between patches, for a total of fourteen models.
- Six files with extensions “.sch” (e.g. “PICO_ALP_Hi_Heatwatering.sch”). These files describe changes in survival through time because of two provenance scenarios (lo and high) crossed by the three sites (forest - LSA, treeline - USA, and alpine - ALP).
- The results of these models are used to create Figure 5 of the main text.

Climate_Table.zip contains the following:

- Two files, both named “Climate_Table_d0_v20160607EEC_rev20210803”. One is a .csv, and the other is a .xlsx. Both file formats are provided for additional accessibility.
- Data in this file were used to create delta (Δ) values found in Table 1 of the publication.
- Metrics include site, data collection year, and site treatment effects on temperature, snow-free season length, and volumetric water content.

ATWE_allplots_GIS.zip contains the following:

- A total of 45 individual files that translate into seven ESRI shapefiles (.shp). These files are compatible with any software that can read shapefiles, such as QGIS or ESRI’s ArcMap suite. These files contain site and plot location, as well as bounding box polygons.
- The projection associated with these files is *NAD 83/UTM zone 13N, EPSG: 26913*.

ATWE_KMLs.zip contains the following:

- Four .kml files with point data showing the four corners bounding each of the three study sites.

- 3) The dispersal matrix which we set specifically for each scenario. Dispersal scenarios differed according to seed provenance and incline angle. Patches were assumed to be 1km apart horizontally with either 210 m (high provenance) or 570 m (low provenance) elevational difference between the forest and the alpine site. (Elevation difference between treeline and alpine sites was constant at 110 m). Thus, the incline angle determined the hypotenuse of the right triangle and thus the actual seed dispersal distance between sites.
- 4) After the dispersal matrix there is the correlation structure between patches and the stage matrix and standard deviation in the stage matrix.
- 5) The three mean vital rates matrices, where forest, treeline, and alpine sites had different vital rates matrices based on the observed recruitment rates from the experiment across sites and because of the parameterized increase in vital rates in open canopies (treeline and alpine sites).
- 6) The three matrices for the standard deviation in vital rates.
- 7) The constraints matrix limits some values (i.e. survival cannot be higher than 1!)
- 8) Below the constraints matrix is the initial abundance matrix. This tells you how many individuals are in each of the population stages at the beginning of the simulation (all in the forest site). Recall that smaller trees take up a “fraction of an individual” compared to larger trees. These density-dependent fractions are defined in the next few hundred lines
- 9) The next few hundred lines define the density dependent fractions for individuals.
- 10) Down near the bottom is the “population management”. This is named for the idea that you might want to move (translocate) individuals from one patch to another. However, this is how we implement the impact of the catastrophe.
- 11) The file will be appended with the population model results after the model is run.

Project Description

Understanding how climate warming will affect the demographic rates of different ecotypes is critical to predicting shifts in species distributions. Here we present results from a common garden climate change experiment in which we measured seedling recruitment of lodgepole pine (*Pinus contorta*), a widespread North American conifer that is also planted globally.

Seeds from a low-elevation provenance had greater recruitment to their third year (by 323%) than seeds from a high-elevation provenance across sites within and above its native elevation range, and across climate manipulations. Heating reduced recruitment (by 49%) to the third year of both low- and high-elevation seed sources across the elevation gradient, while watering alleviated some of the negative effects of heating (108% increase in watered plots). Demographic models based on recruitment data from the climate manipulations and long-term observations of adult populations revealed that heating could effectively halt modeled upslope range expansion except when combined with watering. Simulating fire and rapid post-fire forest recovery at lower elevations accelerated lodgepole pine expansion into the alpine, but did not alter final abundance rankings among climate scenarios. Regardless of climate scenario, greater recruitment of low-elevation seeds compensated for longer dispersal distances to treeline, assuming colonization was allowed to proceed over multiple centuries. Our results show that ecotypes from lower elevations within a species' range could enhance recruitment and facilitate upslope range shifts with climate change.

Data and Documentation Access

- Data described in this guide can be found on the U.S. Department of Energy's ESS-DIVE earth science data archive, as well as on the Dryad Digital Repository, at <http://dx.doi.org/10.5061/dryad.tk1v8>.
- The full publication and its supporting materials can be found online, at <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/gcb.13840>.

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1. Data Characteristics

Spatial Coverage

All field data were collected as part of the Alpine Treeline Warming Experiment (ATWE), located on Niwot Ridge, in the Front Range of the Colorado Rocky Mountains, USA. Site location information is provided in the table below, in WGS 84 decimal degrees and in degrees, minutes, seconds (° ‘ “ N, ° ‘ “ W).

Lodgepole pine (*Pinus contorta*) seeds were collected within 3 km of experimental sites, from two elevation ranges (“provenances”): high (between 3070-3300 m) and low (between 2630-2930 m). Seed viability was determined via x-ray in the U.S. Forest Service nursery in Coeur d’Alene, Idaho.

ATWE site locations at plot center

Site	Location in Degrees, Minutes, Seconds	Decimal Degrees N	Decimal Degrees W	Elevation
Lower Subalpine (LSA)	40° 2' 12" N, 105° 32' 55" W	40.036667	-105.548611	3060m
Upper Subalpine (USA)	40° 3' 5" N, 105° 34' 50" W	40.051389	-105.580556	3430m
Alpine (ALP)	40° 3' 16" N, 105° 35' 37" W	40.054444	-105.593611	3540m

ATWE study site bounding box coordinates (decimal degrees)

Site	Northwest Coordinates	Southeast Coordinates	Northeast Coordinates	Southwest Coordinates
Lower Subalpine (LSA)	40.0372327984, -105.5485367804	40.0366771370, -105.5474293342	40.0372327984, -105.5474293342	40.0366771370, -105.5485367804
Upper Subalpine (USA)	40.0515289883, -105.5810412026	40.0511559630, -105.5804451819	40.0515289883, -105.5804451819	40.0511559630, -105.5810412026
Alpine (ALP)	40.0545378322, -105.5942618300	40.0536736148, -105.5933524590	40.0545378322, -105.5933524590	40.0536736148, -105.5942618300

Temporal Coverage

Seeds were sown and accounted for in cohorts, defined as the year in which the seeds germinated. Experimental data were collected between the years of 2011-2014. In 2011, only low-provenance seeds were collected and sown; the seeds were collected in the spring and stratified before sowing, post-snowmelt. In the years after, seeds were collected in autumn, and sown prior to snowfall, between October and November. More information can be found in the “Data Acquisition and Methods” section of this guide, and in the publication.

2. Data File Organization

There are a total of three compressed zip folders (one with model data, one with experimental data, and the third with climate data), two zipped geospatial files, and one R script file associated with this archive:

Climate_Table.zip contains:

- Climate_Table_d0_v20160607EEC_rev20210803.csv
- Climate_Table_d0_v20160607EEC_rev20210803.xlsx

Conlisk_etal_GCB2018_model_archive20201202.zip containing (files within each folder are continued in the next several pages):

- gcb13840-sup-0001-supinfo.docx
 - gcb13840-sup-0001-supinfo.pdf
 - Model_archive folder:
 - Fig4ace_PICO_hi_20degrees.csv
 - Fig4bdf_PICO_lo_20degrees.csv
 - Fig6ace_PICO_hi_20degrees_FIRE.csv
 - Fig6bdf_PICO_lo_20degrees_FIRE.csv
- Folders within Model_archive:*
- Fire_HighProv
 - Fire_LowProv
 - NoFire_HighProv
 - NoFire_InclineAngle
 - NoFire_LowProv

PICO_seedling_data.zip containing:

- PICOseedlings20160408rev20210127.csv
- PICOseedlings20160408rev20210127.xlsx

R Script file:

- StatsPICO06072016rev12212020.R

Geospatial files:

- **ATWE_KMLs.zip** containing:
 - ALP_bbox.kml
 - ATWE_sites.kml
 - LSA_bbox.kml
 - USA_bbox.kml

ATWE_allplots_GIS.zip containing 45 items contributing to seven shapefiles:

- ALP_bbox.shp (.cpg, .dbf, .prj, .qpj, .shp, .shx)
- ALPS_plots.shp (.cpg, .dbf, .prj, .qpj, .shp, .shx)
- LSA_bbox.shp (.cpg, .dbf, .prj, .qpj, .shp, .shx)
- LSA_plots.shp (.dbf, .prj, .sbn, .sbx, .shp, .shp.xml, .shx)
- sites.shp (.dbf, .prj, .sbn, .sbx, .shp, .shp.xml, .shx)
- USA_bbox.shp (.cpg, .dbf, .prj, .qpj, .shp, .shx)
- USA_plots.shp (.dbf, .prj, .sbn, .sbx, .shp, .shp.xml, .shx)

.pdf file:

- Conlisk_et_al_2018_Data_Users_Guide.pdf

Listed below are the file organizations of all folders within **Model_archive**.

- Folder **Fire_HighProv** containing:
 - Conifer_2014.dpr
 - Conifer_low_mort_2014.dll
 - Fig6ace_PICO_FIRE_control_hi_20degrees.txt
 - Fig6ace_PICO_FIRE_heat_hi_20degrees.txt
 - Fig6ace_PICO_FIRE_heatwater_hi_20degrees.txt
 - Fig6ace_PICO_FIRE_water_hi_20degrees.txt
 - PICO_ALP_Hi_Heating.sch
 - PICO_ALP_Hi_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_FIRE_seeds_3yrs.fch
 - PICO_LSA_Hi_Heating.sch
 - PICO_LSA_Hi_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_post_FIRE.pch
 - PICO_USA_Hi_Heating.sch
 - PICO_USA_Hi_Heatwatering.sch

- Folder **Fire_LowProv** containing:
 - Conifer_2014.dpr
 - Conifer_low_mort_2014.dll
 - Fig6bdf_PICO_FIRE_control_lo_20degrees.txt
 - Fig6bdf_PICO_FIRE_heat_lo_20degrees.txt
 - Fig6bdf_PICO_FIRE_heatwater_lo_20degrees.txt
 - Fig6bdf_PICO_FIRE_water_lo_20degrees.txt
 - PICO_ALP_Lo_Heating.sch
 - PICO_ALP_Lo_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_FIRE_seeds_3yrs.fch
 - PICO_LSA_Lo_Heating.sch
 - PICO_LSA_Lo_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_post_FIRE.pch
 - PICO_USA_Lo_Heating.sch
 - PICO_USA_Lo_Heatwatering.sch

- Folder **NoFire_HighProv** containing:
 - Conifer_low_mort_2014.dll
 - Fig4ace_PICO_control_hi_20degrees.txt
 - Fig4ace_PICO_heat_hi_20degrees.txt
 - Fig4ace_PICO_heatwater_hi_20degrees.txt
 - Fig4ace_PICO_water_hi_20degrees.txt
 - PICO_ALP_Hi_Heating.sch

- PICO_ALP_Hi_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_LSA_Hi_Heating.sch
 - PICO_LSA_Hi_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_USA_Hi_Heating.sch
 - PICO_USA_Hi_Heatwatering.sch
- Folder **NoFire_InclineAngle** containing:
 - Conifer_low_mort_2014.dll
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_hi_15degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_hi_20degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_hi_25degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_hi_30degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_hi_35degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_hi_40degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_hi_45degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_lo_15degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_lo_20degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_lo_25degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_lo_30degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_lo_35degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_lo_40degrees.txt
 - Fig5_PICO_heatwater_lo_45degrees.txt
 - PICO_ALP_Hi_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_ALP_Lo_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_LSA_Hi_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_LSA_Lo_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_USA_Hi_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_USA_Lo_Heatwatering.sch
- Folder **NoFire_LowProv** containing:
 - Conifer_low_mort_2014.dll
 - Fig4bdf_PICO_control_lo_20degrees.txt
 - Fig4bdf_PICO_heat_lo_20degrees.txt
 - Fig4bdf_PICO_heatwater_lo_20degrees.txt
 - Fig4bdf_PICO_water_lo_20degrees.txt
 - PICO_ALP_Lo_Heating.sch
 - PICO_ALP_Lo_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_LSA_Lo_Heating.sch
 - PICO_LSA_Lo_Heatwatering.sch
 - PICO_USA_Lo_Heating.sch
 - PICO_USA_Lo_Heatwatering.sch

3. Data Dictionary

The section below contains detailed descriptions of each heading/field for .csv/.xlsx data files in this archive. Example data records are also provided, as snapshots of each file. The aim of this is to explain file contents in detail, and to provide a pre-download preview of data.

Data values in rows 19-22 are calculations complete with values presented in Table 1 of the journal. The .xlsx version of the file contains actual formula with unrounded values, while the .csv version contains the same values rounded to shorter significant figures.

Alpine site climate data in this file only includes those in the seeded alpine plots (“ALPS”).

File name: Climate_Table_d0_v20160607EEC_rev20210803.csv/.xlsx

Heading	Units/Format	Description
Sites	LSA, USA, ALPS	Site of climate data collection within ATWE: LSA = lower subalpine, 3060 m USA = upper subalpine, 3430 m, ALPS = alpine seeded sites, 3540 m
Year	yyyy	Year of data collection; 2011-2015.
Heat_Delta_T	°C, degrees celsius	Heating treatment effect on soil temperature at 5-10cm
H_T_StdErr	°C, degrees celsius	Standard error for heating effect on soil temperature at 5-10cm
Heat_Delta_VWC	m ³ m ⁻³	Heating effect on volumetric water content at 5-10cm
H_VWC_StdErr	m ³ m ⁻³	Standard error for heating effect on volumetric water content at 5-10cm
Delta_SL	days	Change in snow-free season length due to heating treatment
Water_Delta_T	°C, degrees celsius	Change in 5-10cm soil temperature due to watering treatment
W_T_StdErr	°C, degrees celsius	Standard error for change in 5-10cm soil temperature due to watering treatment
Water_Delta_VWC	m ³ m ⁻³	Change in 5-10cm volumetric water content due to watering treatment
W_VWC_StdErr	m ³ m ⁻³	Standard error for 5-10cm changes in soil volumetric water content due to watering treatment

Example data record

```
Sites,Year,Heat_Delta_T,H_T_StdErr,Heat_Delta_VWC,H_VWC_StdErr,Delta_SL,Water_Delta_T,W_T_StdErr,Water_Delta_VWC,W_VWC_StdErr
ALPS,2011,1.1,0.07,-0.02,0.001,3,-0.13,0.02,0.01,0.002
LSA,2011,4.08,0.05,-0.02,0.001,21,0.17,0.03,0.01,0.001
USA,2011,1.04,0.07,-0.01,0.001,-2,0.25,0.02,0.01,0.001
ALPS,2012,1.42,0.04,-0.01,0.001,16,-0.09,0.02,0.01,0.001
LSA,2012,4.31,0.06,-0.02,0.001,39,0.29,0.02,0.01,0.001
USA,2012,1.72,0.07,-0.02,0.001,17,0.27,0.02,0.01,0.002
ALPS,2013,1.5,0.08,-0.01,0.002,10,-0.02,0.02,0.01,0.002
LSA,2013,3.54,0.08,0,0.003,38,0.07,0.03,0.02,0.001
USA,2013,1.65,0.13,-0.01,0.001,11,0.33,0.01,0.01,0.002
ALPS,2014,1.02,0.06,-0.01,0.001,13,0.06,0.01,0.01,0.001
LSA,2014,3.69,0.07,0,0.001,17,0.48,0.03,0.03,0.001
USA,2014,1.05,0.11,0,0.001,14,0.38,0.01,0.01,0.001
ALPS,2015,1,0.07,-0.01,0.001,14,-0.05,0.03,0.02,0.002
LSA,2015,3.75,0.07,0.01,0.001,38,0.57,0.02,0.02,0.001
USA,2015,-0.03,0.08,0.02,0.001,-1,0.09,0.02,0.01,0.002
,,,,,,,,,
,,,,,,,,,
Mean 2011-2015 (except 2015 H effects),,,,,,,,,,
ALPS,Mean,1.208,0.029257478,-0.012,0.000565685,11.2,-0.046,0.009380832,0.012,0.000748331
LSA,Mean,3.874,0.029866369,-0.006,0.00072111,30.6,0.316,0.01183216,0.018,0.000447214
USA,Mean,1.365,0.049244289,-0.01,0.0005,10,0.264,0.007483315,0.008,0.000748331
```


For columns indicating seedling survival and germination, 0's indicate that no seedlings survived/germinated, while NA's indicate that the value was not measured.

Heading	Units/Format	Description
order	#####	Numerical order of original data entry
Site	LSA, USA, or ALP	Site of data collection within ATWE: LSA = lower subalpine, 3060 m USA = upper subalpine, 3430 m, ALP = alpine, 3540 m
Treat	C, H, W, or HW	Site treatment: C = control, H = heated, W = watered, HW = heated and watered
Heat	1 or 0	Plot heating. 1 = heated, 0 = not heated
Water	1 or 0	Plot watering. 1 = watered, 0 = not watered
Plot	1 - 80	Numbered plots within ATWE: Plots 1-20 were in LSA, 21-40 in USA, and 41-80 in ALP. Twenty plots within ALP were used to study alpine forb communities, and were not included in this experiment.
Quad	a, b, c, or d	ATWE plot quadrat - a, b, c, d. See publication for additional plot setup information
SdlgType	C, D, E, or F	Seedling type: C = 2011 germinant D = 2012 germinant E = 2013 germinant F = 2014 germinant
CohortYear	2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, or 2014	The year seeds emerged, for seeds sown the previous year
Species	PiCo	PiCo = lodgepole pine (<i>Pinus contorta</i>)

Prov	Lo or Hi	Location/approximate elevation of seed source; Lo = 2910 - 3240 m Hi = 3370 - 3570 m
SeedsSown	#####	Number of seeds sown in a particular year; the number of seeds sown varied depending on seed availability per year
SnK2015	#####	Seeds sown, minus all kills (see row below). Data in this column is defined as [(seeds sown) - (seeds killed)]
kills	##	Total number of seedlings killed; some individuals were killed every year for physiological experiments.
k2011	#	2011 kills
k2012	#	2012 kills
k2013	##	2013 kills
k2014	##	2014 kills
germs	####	Total number of germinants
missedGdate	####	The number of seedlings where the germination date was missed
GnK	####	Germinants not killed between 2011-2014
sS2011	####	Survived summer 2011
sW2011	####	Survived winter 2011
sS2012	####	Survived summer 2012
sW2012	####	Survived winter 2012
sS2013	####	Survived summer 2013
sW2013	####	Survived winter 2013
sS2014	####	Survived summer 2014
sS2015	####	Survived summer 2015
sS1	####	Survived one summer season
sW1	####	Survived one winter season
sS2	####	Survived two summers
sW2	####	Survived two winters

sS3	###	Survived three summers
sW3	##	Survived three winters
sS4	###	Survived four summers
sW4	###	Survived four winters. This was not monitored in 2015, so this column is NA.
sS5	###	Survived five summers
First2012	yyyy.###; [year].[fraction of year]	First 2012 survey of previous year's seedlings. This number was not recorded in 2011, since only low-provenance seeds were sown.
First2013	yyyy.###; [year].[fraction of year]	First 2013 survey of previous year's seedlings
First2014	yyyy.###; [year].[fraction of year]	First 2014 survey of previous year's seedlings
First2015	yyyy.###; [year].[fraction of year]	First 2015 survey of previous year's seedlings
Med_G_Date	yyyy.###; [year].[fraction of year]	Median seed germination date; this was not recorded for the 2014 cohort.

Example data record

This screenshot is of the .csv version of PICOseedlings20160408rev20210127.

```

order, Site, Treat, Heat, Water, Plot, Quad, SdLgType, CohortYear, Species, Prov, SeedsSown, SnK2015, kills, k2011, k2012, k2013, k2014, germs, missedGdate, GnK, sS2011, sW20
11, sS2012, sW2012, sS2013, sW2013, sS2014, sS2015, sS1, sW1, sS2, sW2, sS3, sW3, sS4, sW4, sS5, First2012, First2013, First2014, First2015, Med_G_Date
360, ALP, HW, 1, 1, 80, b, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 46, 0, 46, 21, 10, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 21, 10, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, NA, 0, 2012.27, 2013.427, 2014.425, 2015.696, 2011.553
313, USA, C, 0, 0, 37, a, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 31, 0, 31, 6, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 6, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, NA, 0, 2012.434, 2013.488, 2014.523, 2015.707, 2011.584
325, ALP, HW, 1, 1, 48, b, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 23, 0, 23, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, NA, 0, 2012.484, 2013.463, 2014.556, 2015.712, 2011.592
243, LSA, W, 0, 1, 2, a, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 42, 0, 42, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.32, 2013.408, 2014.427, 2015.742, 2011.542
245, LSA, HW, 1, 1, 3, b, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 25, 0, 25, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.265, 2013.441, 2015.742, 2015.742, 2011.553
246, LSA, HW, 1, 1, 3, d, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 11, 0, 11, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.265, 2013.499, NA, NA, 2011.573
247, LSA, H, 1, 0, 4, a, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 95, 95, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 6, 0, 6, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.374, 2013.499, NA, NA, 2011.532
248, LSA, H, 1, 0, 4, b, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 100, 100, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 15, 0, 15, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.355, 2013.441, 2014.468, NA, 2011.532
251, LSA, H, 1, 0, 6, b, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.355, 2013.441, NA, NA, 2011.545
252, LSA, H, 1, 0, 6, c, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 7, 0, 7, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.355, NA, NA, NA, 2011.545
257, LSA, HW, 1, 1, 9, a, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 5, 0, 5, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.355, NA, 2014.384, NA, 2011.545
258, LSA, HW, 1, 1, 9, c, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 23, 0, 23, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.295, 2013.441, 2014.463, NA, 2011.507
259, LSA, C, 0, 0, 10, a, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 115, 115, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 24, 0, 24, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.486, NA, 2014.507, NA, 2011.532
260, LSA, C, 0, 0, 10, b, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 31, 0, 31, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.549, 2013.575, 2014.427, NA, 2011.532
261, LSA, C, 0, 0, 11, b, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 32, 0, 32, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.74, 2013.575, 2014.438, 2015.742, 2011.564
262, LSA, C, 0, 0, 11, d, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 29, 0, 29, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, NA, 2013.575, 2014.438, 2015.742, 2011.564
263, LSA, HW, 1, 1, 12, c, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 24, 0, 24, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.374, 2013.479, 2014.463, NA, 2011.512
264, LSA, HW, 1, 1, 12, d, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 48, 0, 48, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.265, 2013.479, 2014.384, NA, 2011.512
265, LSA, HW, 1, 1, 13, b, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 110, 110, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 9, 0, 9, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.374, NA, 2014.389, NA, 2011.545
266, LSA, HW, 1, 1, 13, c, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 115, 115, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 18, 0, 18, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.374, 2013.46, 2014.748, NA, 2011.545
267, LSA, H, 1, 0, 14, b, C, 2011, PiCo, Lo, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 11, 0, 11, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, NA, 0, 2012.281, 2013.479, NA, NA, 2011.545

```

4. Companion Files

- The full publication and its supplementary files can be accessed online, at <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/gcb.13840>.
- Data files containing models and their results can be accessed on ESS-DIVE, as well as in the Dryad Digital Repository, at <http://dx.doi.org/10.5061/dryad.tk1v>.

5. Quality Assessment

All data entered from field sheets and notebooks were visually verified prior to use in analysis.

The full model assumptions are contained in the documents described above. Model assumptions were examined by co-authors EC and LK, and model results were examined by all co-authors.

The RAMAS software has been used in publications for over 25 years, with periodic updating and additions of functionality. In this data package, we used [RAMAS Metapop](#) Version 5.

6. Data Acquisition and Methods

Experimental sites and treatments

Beginning in 2010, we established lodgepole pine (*Pinus contorta* Douglas var. *latifolia*) common garden experiments at three sites along an elevational gradient at Niwot Ridge in the Colorado Front Range, on the eastern slope of the Rocky Mountains (Castanha, Torn, Germino, Weibel, & Kueppers, 2012): (i) a mature subalpine forest containing a mixture of lodgepole pine, Engelmann spruce (*Picea engelmannii* Parry ex. Engelm), subalpine fir (*Abies lasiocarpa* (Hooker) Nuttall) and limber pine (*Pinus flexilis*), with little herb cover, and near the lower elevation (3,060 m), “warm edge” of mixed subalpine forest and in the midst of lodgepole pine’s elevation range, (ii) an open meadow surrounded by krummholz mats and low-tree islands near the climatically “cool edge” of subalpine forest (3,430 m), and (iii) an alpine meadow approximately 400 m above timberline at 3,540 m (Figure 1 of publication). Lodgepole pine was a major constituent in the forest site, but was not present at the treeline and alpine sites. Mean annual air temperatures were 6.5 ± 0.5 , 7.1 ± 0.5 , and $9.8 \pm 0.4^\circ\text{C}$ for alpine, treeline, and forest sites, respectively, with snow-free growing season lengths of 140, 133, and 157 days (Table 1 of publication). Each site had 20 3-meter diameter plots assigned to one of four groups: control, heated, watered, and heated and watered (Figure 1 of publication). Plots were primarily SE-facing, spanning $79\text{--}194^\circ$ across all sites with shallow slopes spanning $4\text{--}16^\circ$. Six 1000W MorTM ceramic infrared heaters were arrayed around the perimeter of heated plots, following the geometry of Kimball et al. (2008). Active infrared heaters have significant methodological advantages, including nighttime heating and the ability to modify snowmelt timing (Aronson & McNulty, 2009), but do not typically affect air temperature and therefore relative humidity. Heater output was set to a constant 40% of maximum wattage (estimated 170 W/m^2 incident on the plots under low-wind conditions) in all sites during spring and summer months. Heaters were turned down to 10% ($\sim 40 \text{ W/m}^2$) during the windiest period of the year — mid November to early March — to avoid hydrological artifacts and intermittent snowpack (Meromy, Molotch, Williams, Musselman, & Kueppers, 2015). We raised and lowered heater scaffolding in alpine and treeline sites to keep heaters above the snow, repositioning them after snowmelt. We designed the watering treatments (2.5 mm per week) to compensate for the evaporative losses due to heating (determined at the start of the project from observed differences in the rate of forest soil drying at different temperatures), adding water manually once per week starting 2–3 weeks after snowmelt and ending in September.

The added water, which was melted snow or locally pumped groundwater, amounted to a maximum of $\sim 5\%$ ($\sim 43 \text{ mm}$ added) of the long-term average annual total precipitation at the sites (808 mm; Moyes, Germino, & Kueppers, 2015). Less water was added to treeline plots and to unheated plots, which melted weeks later than other plots. All plots were divided into four $1 \times 1 \text{ m}$ quadrants (Figure 1 of publication). To document microclimate conditions, we placed one soil moisture and temperature sensor (ECTM or 5TM, Decagon Devices) at 5–10 cm depth in the center of each quadrant (4 per plot) and wired them to multiplexers and CR1000 dataloggers (Campbell Scientific). During the snow-free periods of 2011–2015 (the period of this study), mean daily soil temperature was greater in heated than unheated plots, with larger differences (3.9°C) in the forest than in the alpine (1.2°C) because of higher wind speed at the alpine site (Table 1 of publication). At the treeline site, soil temperature increase due to heating was similar to the alpine site (1.4°C) in 2011–2014. In 2015, many heaters at the treeline site failed; thus, 2015 is excluded from statistical analysis of heating effects.

Heating alone tended to reduce soil moisture slightly, even in the alpine and at treeline (Table 1 of publication). Finally, heating advanced the timing of snowmelt in all years and all sites with the exception of the treeline site in 2011. The shortest snow-free seasons were observed in 2011 and 2013. Watering did not significantly alter the plot temperature range, but slightly increased soil moisture in all sites (Table 1 of publication).

Seedling observations

We collected lodgepole pine seeds from high-elevation (3070–3300 m) and low-elevation (2630–2930 m) locations within 3 km of the experimental sites. The 2011 cohort (defined as the year in which the seeds germinated) consisted only of low-provenance seeds which were collected in the spring and stratified for 8 weeks prior to sowing after snowmelt. Seeds for the 2012–2014 cohorts were collected in fall and sown prior to snowfall, during the October–November. The lodgepole pine seeds were assigned to twenty-four 10×10 cm cells crisscrossing each quadrant. Low-provenance seed was assigned to quadrants containing Engelmann spruce in the remaining 70 cells while high-provenance seed was assigned to quadrants containing limber pine in the remaining 70 cells (Figure 1 of publication). We sowed 80–480 lodgepole pine seeds, buried at 1 cm depth, of each cohort per quadrant (a total of 245,000 seeds over 4 cohorts), making an effort to adjust the amount of seed according to viability as determined by x-ray (conducted by the USFS nursery in Coeur D’Alene, ID) and ensure adequate sample sizes. The lower limit on our seed densities is comparable to those seen in nature (Lotan & Perry, 1983). To exclude small granivorous mammals, we placed hardware cloth enclosures over each quadrant.

We tracked the number of seeds sown and number of seedlings surviving to autumn of each year in each cell. We quantified the fraction of seedlings surviving from seed to the autumn of their first year (first-year recruitment), from the autumn of their first year to autumn of their second year (second-year survival), from autumn of their second year to autumn of their third year (third-year survival), and from seed to three years (third-year recruitment). Because new seeds were sown each year (yielding 2011–2014 cohorts), we have the most observations for first-year recruitment (840 observations — with only low-provenance seeds for the 2011 cohort). For second-year survival, if all quadrants had at least one survivor, we would have 800 observations (from seedlings emerging in 2011–2014). Instead, we obtained 490 observations because some quadrants had no individuals surviving their first year and 10 heated plots (40 quadrants) in the treeline site were excluded from the 2014 cohort due to heater failure (Table SI2.1 from the supplementary file shows sample size across cohorts)

Statistical analysis

We estimated the effects of multiple factors on lodgepole pine seedling survival using a generalized linear mixed model (with plot and observation level random effects) with a logit link and binomial distribution in the R programming language (Bates, Maechler, Bolker, & Walker, 2015; R Core Team, 2017). Significance levels were estimated using likelihood ratio tests. Because GLMM likelihood ratio tests in R (`lme4::glmer`) do not automatically compute a likelihood ratio for main effects separately from their interactions, we directly manipulated the design matrix (`stats::model.matrix`) to test main effects. In manipulating the design matrix, we chose sum contrasts (using “`contr.sum`” in R), where model intercepts are the average recruitment (or survival) across all factors and coefficient estimates are the deviation from this average for a given treatment. Thus, contrary to the default output in `lme4::glmer`, all levels across a factor should sum to zero (where there are two

levels, we present just one because the other is the same magnitude but opposite sign). Using a hypothesis-testing framework, which is consistent with a manipulation experiment, we considered main effects (heating, watering, provenance, site, and cohort) and all two-way interactions for first-year recruitment and only main effects for second- and third-year survival and third-year recruitment. We analyzed two subsets of the data: (1) the years in which there is a fully balanced treatment design (cohorts 2012–2014) and (2) all the data taken together, including the 2011 cohort which only had low-provenance seedlings and the 2015 data (in which heated treatments at the treeline site are not included due to heater failure). The first-year recruitment results for the former subset are included in the text, and results for the latter subset are placed in Appendix S1 (found in Supporting Information document “gcb13840-sup-0001-supinfo.docx/.pdf in this archive) and are not qualitatively different. Third-year recruitment results for both subsets are presented below and annual second- and third-year survival for both subsets of data are placed in Appendix S1.

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Data Citation

Dryad

Conlisk, Erin et al. (2018), Data from: Seed origin and warming constrain lodgepole pine recruitment, slowing the pace of population range shifts, Dryad, Dataset, <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.tk1v8>

ESS-DIVE

Conlisk E ; Castanha C ; Germino M J; Veblen T T ; Smith J M ; Moyes A B ; Kueppers L M (2018): Data from: “Seed origin and warming constrain lodgepole pine recruitment, slowing the pace of population range shifts”. Subalpine and Alpine Species Range Shifts with Climate Change: Temperature and Soil Moisture Manipulations to Test Species and Population Responses. doi: 10.5061/dryad.tk1v8.

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Publication

Conlisk E, Castanha C, Germino MJ, et al. Seed origin and warming constrain lodgepole pine recruitment, slowing the pace of population range shifts. *Glob Change Biol.* 2018; 24: 197-211
<https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13840>

ATWE Site Coordinates

C. Castanha, M.S. Torn, M. J. Germino, B. Weibel and L. M. Kueppers. 2013. Conifer seedling recruitment across a gradient from forest to alpine tundra: effects of species, provenance, and site. *Plant Ecology & Diversity*, 6(3-4): 307-318, DOI: 10.1080/17550874.2012.716087

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